

Characterization of $Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ coatings with selective IR reflectivity

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Abstract

$Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ thin films were deposited by reactive magnetron sputtering. The obtained different stoichiometries give rise to different optical properties as the films change from metallic to dielectric. In this work the IR reflectivity of these coatings is investigated taking into account different application fields for IR selective $Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ thin films.

Low Al content coatings present high reflectivity, high absorptance and low thermal emittance. High Al compositions give raise to coatings with high absorptance and high thermal emittance.

The composition of the coatings was evaluated combining electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) and energy dispersive spectroscopy. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) revealed a columnar structure. Reflectance spectra for the visible and infrared spectral ranges were used to obtain the solar absorptance and thermal emittance values, used to calculate the equilibrium temperature of the coatings.

The thermal stability in air from 300 to 600 °C was also evaluated.

Keywords: Selective IR; $Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ coatings; Magnetron sputtering; Space applications; Solar absorbers

1. Introduction

$Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ coatings are known to be relatively hard with superior oxidation resistance, chemical inertness and good thermodynamic stability. In the recent years the field of applications of $Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ coatings has spread from the traditional mechanical cutting tools (Bouzakis et al., 2007) to electronic devices (Cha et al., 2002), solar selective applications (Barshilia et al., 2006; Schu ¨ler et al., 2001) and even to satellite industry (Brogren et al., 2000; Chen et al., 2009). The optical properties of these $Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ coatings

can be tuned in a wide range from metallic to dielectric character by controlling the stoichiometry x .

Different applications fields can be pointed out for selective IR reflectivity: solar-control windows where a high color-neutral transmittance in the visible (VIS), good reflectance at near-infrared and low thermal emittance are important properties (Schu ¨ler et al., 2001); solar absorber collectors with high absorptance in the solar spectrum and low emittance in the infrared (Gelin et al., 2003); and satellite temperature control coatings where the balance between solar absorptance and thermal emittance are crucial to control the temperature, decreasing the absorptance and increasing the emittance of the coatings an equilibrium temperature for the satellite can be achieved.

The solar radiation can be consider as approximately equivalent to that from a blackbody at 5762 K with the

intensity maximum at 500 nm. At 300–400 K the intensity maximum of the blackbody radiation is at 10 μm . The wavelength gap between the maximum of incoming and outgoing radiation gives the possibility to control separately the absorption and emission of a surface by optically selective coatings.

In this work, $\text{Ti}_{1-x}\text{Al}_x\text{N}$ thin films with $0.2 < x < 0.6$ were prepared by reactive magnetron sputtering. Their infrared reflectivity regarding the above-mentioned applications is discussed based on their composition and microstructure.

2. Experimental

Fig. 1 shows a schematic diagram of the deposition chamber used and Table 1 summarizes the synthesis conditions for the $\text{Ti}_{1-x}\text{Al}_x\text{N}$ coatings studied in this work. Pure Ti and pure Al targets were used (Kurt Lesker 99.99%) under dc discharge. The deposition took place in several steps; starting with an argon atmosphere and increasing gradually in nitrogen, keeping the total pressure in the chamber in 1.33 Pa. The purpose is to obtain $\text{Ti}_{1-x}\text{Al}_x\text{N}$ coatings with different x .

Additionally samples have been prepared without gradient underlayer for very short deposition times leading to very thin coatings with same composition in the range of a few tens of nanometers.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed to study the morphology and thickness of samples in a high resolution microscope, HITACHI S5200. The samples were cleaved from coatings grown onto silicon, and were observed without metallization in cross-sectional views at 1–2 kV.

The residual stress of the films on silicon substrates was evaluated by mechanical profilometry according to the Stoney's equation (Stoney, 1909).

The microstructure of these coatings was investigated by grazing incidence X-ray diffraction and electron transmission microscopy with selected area electron diffraction.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the deposition chamber used.

Table 1
Deposition conditions for the studied coatings.

Sample	S200/200			S200/400		
	1	2	3	1	2	3
N ₂ (%)	0	7	15	0	15	30
Dep. time (min)	10	10	130	10	10	130
Thickness (nm)	200		1000	200		1700
Dep. rate (nm/min)	10		8	10		13
Target power (W)	Ti 200 W dc Al 200 W dc			Ti 200 W dc Al 400 W dc		

The Grazing Incidence X-ray Diffraction (GIXRD) equipment used was a Siemens D5000 working with Cu K α radiation. For GIXRD analysis samples deposited on steel were used.

A Philips CM200 Transmission Electron Microscope equipped with a parallel detection electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) spectrometer from Gatan (766–2 kV) was used. For TEM analysis thin foils were prepared from cross-sectioned slices of coatings deposited on silicon (1 0 0) using an ion milling system. Energy electron loss spectroscopy and energy dispersive spectroscopy were used on the TEM to analyse the composition of the films.

Near IR and IR reflectivity measurements in the spectral range of 0.5–2.5 and 1.3–200 μm respectively, have been done using IFS 66 v/s (BRUKER) infrared Fourier-transform spectrometer with reflection units at the near normal incidence and at the oblique angles of incidence up to the grazing angles (reflection–absorption spectroscopy (RAS)) in polarized light for samples grown on steel substrates. The spectral resolution was 4 cm^{-1} .

In the visible range the (0.4–0.8 μm) the coatings total reflectance was measured in a Shimadzu UV-2101PC spectrometer equipped with an integrating sphere. Barium sulphate was used as reference. The measurements were performed on coated steel substrates.

The solar absorptance, a , and the emittance $e(T)$ were calculated from the definition (Duffie and Beckman, 1980):

$$a = \frac{\int_0^\infty a_k P_k^i dk}{\int_0^\infty P_k^i dk}$$

$$e(T) = \frac{\int_0^\infty e_k P_k^b(T) dk}{\int_0^\infty P_k^b(T) dk}$$

where P^i and $P^b(T)$ are the incident spectral solar radiant

power and the temperature dependent, spectral blackbody radiant power. The spectral absorptance a , and the spectral hemispherical emittance, e , are material-dependent parameters that can be determined from optical measurements.

In the case of opaque films the absorptance a_k and emittance e_k are given by the Kirchhoff's law.

$$a_k = 1 - q_k \quad (3)$$

$$e_k = 1 - q_k \quad (4)$$

where q_k is the reflectance at wavelength k . The emittance was calculated according to Eq. (2) at 373 K.

For a body exposed to the solar radiation the equilibrium temperature of the body is controlled by the incoming solar radiation and the outgoing emitted radiation as well as the eventual heat generated by the body itself. If the generated power is neglected the emitted power and absorbed power should be equal at the equilibrium temperature according to the Stefan–Boltzmann law and the equilibrium temperature is given by:

$$T = 4 \frac{Sa}{4er} \quad (5)$$

where r is the Stefan–Boltzmann constant and $S = 1353 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ the solar constant.

Several applications in the field of solar power require high thermal stability. The thermal stability of the $\text{Ti}_{1-x}\text{Al}_x\text{N}$ thin films was also investigated. The coatings were subjected to different annealing treatments, from 300 to 600 °C in air for 1 h, and GIXRD was employed to study microstructural changes.

3. Results and discussion

Table 2 presents the chemical composition of the coatings given by EELS and EDAX.

By controlling the deposition parameters samples with different stoichiometry x of $\text{Ti}_{1-x}\text{Al}_x\text{N}$ were obtained. XPS results not presented, show similar composition for the very thin samples.

Due to the vacuum conditions and the high reactivity of Ti and Al towards oxygen it is not possible to exclude the incorporation of oxygen in the films. Lower deposition rates (see thickness values on Table 1) seem also to favour the incorporation of oxygen in the films (Prochařka et al., 2004). This is the case of sample S200/200.

Fig. 2 shows the morphology of the samples in planar view and cross section. A columnar growth typical of samples grown under low adatom mobility as described by zone 1 of Thornton’s model (Thornton, 1977) is observed.

The oxygen contamination can also be due to the columnar structure of the films and the open voids between columns.

In planar view it is possible to observe that the columns end in a pyramidal shape typical of $\text{Ti}_{1-x}\text{Al}_x\text{N}$ coatings (Schüller et al., 2001).

The microstructure of these coatings was evaluated by GIXRD. Fig. 3 shows the different diffraction pattern of these samples.

As the Al content increases there is a displacement in the diffraction peaks to higher 2θ . The lattice parameter of

Fig. 2. SEM-FEG cross-sectional and planar micrographs

Fig. 3. Grazing incidence XRD diffraction pattern: $x = 0.21$ and 0.58 .

Fig. 4. Lattice parameters as function of Al content.

Table 2

Chemical composition as given by EELS and EDAX.

Samples	N_2 (%)	Composition (at.%)				x
		Ti	Al	N	O	
S200/200	15	39	10	28	23	0.21
S200/400	30	21	29	37	13	0.58

these coatings as a function of x in $\text{Ti}_{1-x}\text{Al}_x\text{N}$ is shown in Fig. 4. Also literature results are included for comparison (Ikeda and Stoh, 1991; Zhou et al., 1999).

Adding gradually Al to the cubic TiN phase leads to a decrease of lattice parameters caused by the substitution of Ti atoms by Al atoms with smaller atomic radius; shifting the $2h$ peaks in $Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ to higher values as compared to TiN. Many authors have investigated the phase relations in the ternary Ti-Al-N system (Ikeda and Stoh, 1991; Zhou et al., 1999). In general all agree that for low Al content a single phase solid solution c-(Ti, Al)N is present and for higher Al content a dual-phase structure of c-(Ti, Al)N and h-AlN can be found, a further increase in the Al composition leads to a single phase h-AlN (see Fig. 4). The limits of these regions are not always the same for the different authors. The immiscibility zone limits described by Ikeda are around $x = 0.7$ while for Zhou there's a region between $x = 0.6$ and 0.7 where the phases co-exist and for $x > 0.7$ only a single hexagonal phase is present. It is also possible that the deposition parameters play a major role in the limits of each zone phases (Zhou et al., 1999). In our case the hexagonal aluminium nitride phase could not be detected by XRD.

Also no crystalline oxide phases were found. The high oxygen contamination is probably leading to the formation of amorphous oxide or oxynitride phases of Ti and Al.

Other parameter that can contribute to the $2h$ shift in the XRD is the residual stress of the coatings. Tensile stresses increase the distances between the planes shifting the peaks to lower positions while compressive stresses make them move to higher $2h$ peaks. The residual stress of these films is presented in Table 3.

The reflectance spectra of the $Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ films with different thicknesses, deposited on steel are presented in Fig. 5.

In the case of the thick samples, both compositions present very low reflectivity in the visible range (Fig. 5a). In the infrared region the spectra are very different. For a low Al content, $x = 0.21$ the reflectance is very high, around 0.9

Table 3
Residual stress of the films as given by Stoney equation.

Samples	x	Residual stress (MPa)
S200/200	0.21	217
S200/400	0.58	89

for wavelengths higher than 10 μm , similar to TiN (Brogren et al., 2000). Higher Al content reduces the infrared reflectivity.

The solar absorptance (a) and infrared emittance (e) in Table 4 were calculated according to Duffie and Beckman (1980) at 373 K.

The highest content in aluminium results in low infrared reflectance and high emittance giving the lowest equilibrium temperature, as already observed by other authors (Brogren et al., 2000). These characteristics make it suitable for example for satellite temperature control. While the low emittance and high absorptance of sample S200/200 are adequate for solar absorbers.

Also the thickness of the coatings seems to play an important role in what concerns the equilibrium temperature of the films, interference effects can be used to tune the solar absorptance and thermal emission modifying the equilibrium temperature (Brogren et al., 2000; Chen et al., 2009). Very thin films (50–60 nm) were also deposited in the same conditions as previous samples and their absorptance and IR emittance were calculated as well as their equilibrium temperature and presented in Table 4. For the higher Al content the changes in e are now more significant resulting in a very high increase of the equilibrium temperature.

The thermal stability of these coatings was also investigated. In solar thermal power plants for example, working temperatures of 400 °C require air-stable materials that can resist this high temperature (Yin et al., 2007). Annealing treatments were performed in air from 300 to 600 °C (1 h) on sample S200/200 which was more suitable for this kind of application. The structure evolution was followed by GIXRD (Fig. 6).

Table 4
Calculated optical properties (absorptance and emittance at 373 K) and equilibrium temperature for $Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ samples with different x values and thicknesses.

x	t (nm)	a	e	a/e	T (°C)
0.21	1200	0.90	0.24	4.08	114
	50	0.84	0.15	5.40	150
0.58	1900	0.93	0.72	1.29	24
	60	0.79	0.15	5.00	142

Fig. 5. Reflectance spectra of the $Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ samples: (a) in the visible range and (b) in the infrared.

Fig. 6. Diffraction pattern of $Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ samples with different annealing treatments.

Fig. 7. Reflectance spectra of sample S200/200 before and after annealing in air at 400 °C, 1 h.

The coating is stable at least until 300 °C. At 400 °C aluminium oxide phases are fully crystallized.

The reflectance spectrum of this sample was investigated in order to understand how the oxide phases interfere in the reflectivity of the coating. Fig. 7 shows the reflectance of the sample in the visible range.

As before, the sample presents low reflectivity in the main solar radiation range, indicating that the annealing treatment does not much influence the optical properties of the coating in the visible range. The solar absorptance after heat treatment is $a = 0.9$ which makes the coating a suitable candidate for this kind of application.

4. Conclusions

By controlling the deposition parameters, N_2 fraction in the gas phase and power supplied to the Ti and Al targets $Ti_{1-x}Al_xN$ thin films with different stoichiometries can be deposited by reactive magnetron sputtering.

X-ray diffraction indicates the formation of $TiAlN$ phases that displace to higher 2θ peaks with the increase of Al content.

The samples present low reflectivity in the visible range. In the IR two different behaviours appear, depending on the Al content in the film. For low Al amount ($x = 0.21$) high reflectivity is observed closed to that of TiN (Brogren et al., 2000), high absorptance and low thermal emittance give high equilibrium temperatures. For $x = 0.58$ high absorptance and high emittance are achieved and the coating equilibrium temperature is 23 °C.

Regarding these results low Al content coating can be proposed as candidate for solar absorbers while the low equilibrium temperature of the high Al film makes it suitable for satellite temperature control.

One of the requests for solar thermal plants materials is its thermal stability in air without losing the optical properties. For that propose, the reflectivity in the visible range of the best candidate for this application was investigated after annealing treatment in air at 400 °C for 1 h. The microstructure of the annealed coating revealed the formation of oxide phases. Nevertheless the reflectivity in the visible range seems to not be affected by these oxides, and the coating proves to be a good candidate for this application.

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